

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

EBT Cover Letter for **commentary** submissions

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1. Submission data

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We are pleased to submit our manuscript “**A quantitative weight-of-evidence approach for confidence assessment in adverse-outcome pathway networks: Overcoming the barriers**” to *Evidence-Based Toxicology*. We have read EBT’s [Instructions for Authors](#). We have provided below all relevant information and links as per the instructions for authors.

2. Basic information

We confirm that we have provided the following information:

Ref	Y/N	Item
2.1	Y	Full name, affiliations, and ORCIDs (if available) of each author
2.2	Y	Author contributions in the form of a CRediT statement (authors may find Tenzing helpful)
2.3	N	Complete funding details
2.4	Y	A fully-informative disclosure of interests for all authors (suggested template)
2.5	N	3 rd -party data and program code are fully cited (data standard: TOP 1, level 3)

We ask for a **CrediT statement** (item 2.2) to support making it easier to find and share information about author contributions. Authors may find the [Tenzing app](#) useful for CrediT statements (please remember to cite it, as per item 2.6). For **disclosures of interest**, we request both financial and non-financial interests to be declared; authors may find [this DOI template](#) helpful. For 3rd party data and code, we seek to comply with TOP data standards (specifically Top 1, Level 3: [click here for more information](#)).

[Authors: please add any comments or questions about the above here]

3. Index of supplemental materials

We have provided the following supplemental materials alongside our Working Paper:

No supplemental materials.